

Original Article

The influence of reverse flow within side branches on plaque formation in the coronary artery relative to bifurcation angles

COVER LETTER

Dear, Editor

Please find our manuscript entitled “The influence of reverse flow within side branches on plaque formation in the coronary artery relative to bifurcation angles” submitted for consideration for publication in the *Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics*.

The occurrence of atherosclerotic lesions at the coronary bifurcation tends to progress confined to specific areas depending on blood flow patterns. We numerically investigated the three-dimensional bifurcation flow of a coronary artery, where a side branch vessel with the same cross-sectional area as the main vessel branches off from the main straight vessel at a given bifurcation angle. We examined the effect of the bifurcation angle on the flow characteristics around the bifurcation region, including wall shear stress, static pressure, the size of the reverse flow zone, and the distribution of flow rate to the side branch vessel.

We are sending the original manuscript with figures and movies. I would sincerely appreciate your review and consideration of this manuscript for publication in *Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics*. The manuscript has never been published before and is not under consideration for publication elsewhere. All authors have read and approved the manuscript and ensure that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved. None of the authors have any relationship with a related industry.

Finally, we would like to recommend the following two reviewers:

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(2) Bon-Kwon Koo, MD, PhD (bkkoo@snu.ac.kr), Professor, Director of Cardiovascular Center and Chair in Cardiology Division, Seoul National University Hospital, Seoul.

We thank you in advance for your consideration.

On behalf of the authors with warm regards,

ABSTRACT

The occurrence of atherosclerotic lesions in the coronary bifurcation tends to progress confined to specific areas depending on blood flow patterns. We conducted a numerical investigation into the three-dimensional bifurcation flow of the coronary artery, focusing on a side branch vessel branching off at a specified bifurcation angle. This study examined the impact of the bifurcation angle on flow characteristics around the bifurcation region, including wall shear stress, static pressure, the size of the reverse flow zone, and the flow rate distribution to the side branch vessel. Unsteady pulsatile flow has been considered at $Re=312$ assuming blood as a Newtonian fluid. Our numerical results indicate that as the bifurcation angle increases, the pressure drop between the inlet and outlet increases, while the flow rate to the side branch vessel decreases. Additionally, in our study, a reverse flow zone near the outer wall of the side branch was observed, and it was found that the reverse flow becomes stronger as the bifurcation angle increases due to the lower momentum of blood near the outer wall and the central part of the side branch vessel. The height of reverse flow zone of the side branch rapidly increases as the bifurcation angle increases up to about 60 degrees and then mildly saturates as the bifurcation angle increases. Flow stagnation in the reverse flow zone of the side branch may promote platelet aggregation and lipid deposition, accelerating the formation of atherosclerotic plaques.

Keywords: Bifurcation angle; Atherosclerotic plaque; Coronary artery; Reverse flow

ABBREVIATIONS

WSS = wall shear stress

BA = bifurcation angle

MV = main vessel

SB = side branch vessel

ISR = in-stent restenosis

ESS = endothelial shear stress

PCI = percutaneous coronary intervention

LM = left main coronary artery

LAD = left anterior descending coronary artery

MACCE = major adverse cardiac and cerebrovascular events

DCB = drug coated balloon

FFR = fractional flow reserve

INTRODUCTION

Hemodynamic factors have been used to explain the progression of atherosclerosis in the coronary artery. Caro et al. showed that areas with low endothelial wall shear stress (WSS) are associated with the occurrence and localization of atherosclerosis through a coronary artery model based on autopsy and a computational fluid dynamics study of carotid bifurcation (1-3). Other studies suggest that high oscillatory shear stress occurs at local sites during the systolic phase, which may be a flow condition that promotes the atherosclerotic process at those sites (4). These local hemodynamic stress distributions change most dynamically with geometric morphology in the coronary bifurcation region (5). Larger angles of the main vessel (MV) and side branch vessels (SB) decrease the WSS on the wall opposite the carina, and significantly increase the oscillatory shear stress around the carina, which promotes the proliferation of plaques in the bifurcation region (6,7). Previous studies have shown that larger MV-SB angles are independently related to the initial atherosclerotic changes in the bifurcation region (8,9). Clinical data also have shown that SB of the coronary arteries with large angles of MV-SB have been reported to have more severe SB outer wall (opposite to the carina side) disease than smaller angles (10). In particular, the distribution of low endothelial WSS in these regions has been demonstrated through experiments (11,12). This trend continues with a model of coronary arteries covered with implanted stents. No matter what technique is used to insert a stent at the bifurcation, it is known that in-stent restenosis (ISR) is more likely to occur at the SB outer wall (13,14). Even in the case of bifurcation lesions treated with stents, clinical results have been reported to be poor with a large bifurcation angle (BA) (15). However, this remains controversial due to existing clinical studies' lack of statistical power to determine the effect of BA on stenosis. Additionally, setting a specific cutoff angle to assess risk is challenging.

There have been several previous studies to create a simulation model to reveal BA related mechanisms involved in the progression of stenosis at the bifurcation site. However, most numerical studies examining the impact of BA on the hemodynamics of branch vessels have focused on carotid artery bifurcations, with few studies specifically targeting coronary artery bifurcations that incorporate the pulsation waveforms characteristic of coronary arteries (4,16). Even for coronary-related studies, most of them examined velocity fields and WSS distributions in SB of bifurcating flows for a few selected BAs; no correlation formulae have been proposed between BA and hemodynamic quantities such as flow distribution, size of reverse flow and WSS, etc. (11,12,17).

In this study, we have comprehensively investigated BA's effect on the hemodynamics of coronary bifurcating flow by simulating unsteady equations of the flow field for ten BAs. From the present numerical simulations, some correlations for the maximum WSS and the size of the reverse flow zone of a SB have been proposed as a function of BA and the dependency of other hemodynamic quantities such as flow distribution, pressure drop on BA of coronary bifurcating flow also examined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Numerical method

ANSYS 2020R2 solved the present problems by using a polyhedron mesh shown in Fig.1A SIMPLE algorithm has been employed both for transient simulations. Second-order upwind scheme was used for the spatial discretization of momentum equation and the second order Crank-Nicolson method employed for the temporal discretization. Both momentum and continuity equations were iteratively solved until the residuals were less than 10^{-5} .

The effect of bifurcating angle (BA) on the flow characteristics of the bifurcating flow in a coronary artery is discussed based on the numerical results of unsteady flow simulations with various BAs. The Reynolds number is 312, which is based on the inlet mean velocity, inlet diameter and the kinematic viscosity of blood. Fig.1B shows the evolution of inlet flow rate of a coronary artery used in the present unsteady simulation and a dashed line of Fig.1B denotes the averaged inlet velocity.

Problem description

We have conducted numerical simulations of the bifurcating flow shown in Fig.1C for ten BAs. A uniform flow is assigned at the inlet and zero pressure is imposed at the two outlets and the definitions of $BA(\alpha)$, length and height of reverse flow zone (L_r and H_r), inner and outer wall of SB and distal-MV are provided in Fig.1C. It should be noted that the inlet area of branch vessel increases as BA decreases because a branching vessel of the same diameter as that of the MV is bifurcated from the straight MV. From the present numerical results, the flow on the outer wall side of the bifurcating branch vessel is mostly examined because the possibility of plaque generation is high around that region.

Grid and time-step independence test

We have examined the effect of grid resolution on the average profile of velocity component parallel to the branch vessel near the bifurcating region for eighty degrees of BA. Fig.S1-A compares the profiles for various grid resolutions along a vertical line to the outer wall, which is located 1 mm downstream from the bifurcating point B. The effect of time-step on the evolution of WSS at point A is shown in Fig.S1-B by using the grid resolution of D/40. It shows that the time-step of 0.001s needs to be used for unsteady simulations. A further validation of grid-resolution and time-step is given for 90 degrees of BA in Fig.S1-C. We have confirmed that the evolutions of WSS at point A with BA=90° are indistinguishable for the grid-resolutions of D/30 and D/40 when time-step of 0.001s is used. Following the result of Fig.S1, the grid resolution of D/30 with time-step of 0.001s has been employed for all the simulations of the present study.

RESULTS

Effect of BA on flow rate distribution and pressure drop

Fig.2A plots the ratio (β) of the flow rate into the side-branch vessel to the inlet flow rate for various BAs. It shows that the ratio decreases as BA increases and the trend with time-averaged flow is similar to that at the maximum inlet velocity. It also shows that β decreases mildly as BA increases up to a certain BA ($\sim 50^\circ$), but the decreasing rate is very small for BA $>50^\circ$. It needs to be noted again that the inlet area of side-branch vessel of Fig.1 decreases as BA increases. Therefore, it is conjectured that the bigger inlet area of branch vessel at low BAs may also attribute to the higher flow rate into side-branch vessel. Fig.2B shows that the pressure drop between inlet and the two outlets increases as BA increases implying that the head loss of the bifurcating flow increases with the increase of BA. It also shows that the magnitude of pressure drop slightly increases as BA increases up to a certain BA($\sim 50^\circ$) and then, it is nearly

constant beyond the BA.

Fig.3A compares the contours of time-averaged V_s (velocity parallel to SB) at the cross-section of SB inlet for BA=30 and 90 degrees. It is noted that A/B of line A-B denotes a point on the outer/inner wall and line C-D is orthogonal to line A-B. Fig.3A shows that V_s along line A-B is higher(lower) near the inner(outer) wall side resulting in a higher(lower) WSS whereas V_s near the both ends of line C-D is higher than that near outer wall side of line A-B with being symmetric about the line A-B. To quantify the relative magnitude of flowrate to the inner/outer wall side, V_s profiles are plotted along the lines A-B and C-D for various BAs in Fig.3B and Fig.S2 by using the time-averaged data and the data at the maximum inlet velocity. The left column of Fig.3B confirms that V_s is quite lower in the region of outer wall side regardless of BA while V_s is much higher near the inner wall side with being rapidly lower as BA increases. Therefore, the flow rate along the line A-B decreases with the increase of BA. On the other hand, the right column of Fig.3B reveals that V_s profiles along the line C-D have two maximums near the wall with one minimum located at the center of the cross section and that WSSs on both sides are high regardless of BA implying a lower possibility of flow separation near those walls. It is also noted that the flow rate along the line C-D is bigger with the increase of BA because of the increasing two maximum velocities. This fact explains why the flowrates to SB of BA=30 and 90 degrees differs only by 30 percents although the flowrate to the inner wall side with BA=30 degree is more than two times of that with BA=90. As a result, it can be said that Fig.3B is consistent with the result of Fig.2A that the flow rate to SB mildly decreases with the increase of BA; beta of 30 degrees is only about 1.3 times larger than that of 90 degrees. Fig.4 plots the time-averaged pressure coefficient along the inner/outer wall for three BAs. Adverse pressure gradients are clearly displayed along the outer wall of SB whereas the inner wall is subject to favorable pressure gradient for the three BAs except a small portion near the bifurcating region of BA=30. Considering that the momentum of blood near the outer-wall side,

which is under adverse pressure gradient, is quite small compared to other parts of SB, it can be said that a reverse flow is highly possible to occur along the outer wall side of the bifurcating region and that the larger BA is, the stronger the reverse flow is because of the lower momentum near the outer wall side and the center part of the cross-sectional area (See Fig.3). The contours of y-velocity component for three BAs are shown in Fig.5A. It shows that a stronger vortex with a shorter length of reverse flow zone is generated as BA increases qualitatively confirming the results of the preceding figures. Fig.5B and Fig.5C plots the normalized lengths and heights of reverse flow zones defined in Fig.1 for various BAs. It reveals that the correlations obtained between the length and BA by neglecting a few data at low BAs can be approximated well by a straight line. The correlations are computed as follows:

$$\text{Maximum flow rate: } \frac{L_r}{D} = -0.75 \left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{12} \right) + 2.7$$

$$\text{Time averaged: } \frac{L_r}{D} = -0.49 \left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{9} \right) + 2.0$$

The normalized height tends to rapidly increase with the increase of BA up to around 50°~60° and approaches the asymptotic value of 0.53 as BA increases more. Therefore, it can be said that the larger BA is, the narrower the flow passage of side-branch becomes leading to the occlusion of side-branch vessel (10,13). This is clearly demonstrated by the two animations that show path lines generated by continuously seeding particles at inlet of the computational domain for the case of two BAs of 30 and 90 degrees. We used EnSight to visualize the pathlines and vector fields of the unsteady pulsatile flows for BA=30° (Mov.1) and BA=90° (Mov.2). This analysis demonstrated that low flow rate areas and stagnation zones form on the outer wall of the SB (mainly near the ostium) and the outer wall of the MV (relatively distal to the ostium).

Effect of BA on WSS distribution

To investigate the effect of BA on WSS distribution, WSS related to the reverse flow zone shown in the animations of the preceding section are examined. Fig.6A shows WSS contours on the reverse flow zone of SB vessel for three selected BAs. It shows that the larger BA is, the stronger/wider the reverse flow zone is. It also reveals that WSS has two maximum values when $BA > 50^\circ$ with the maximum(P2) near the bifurcating region being greater than the maximum(P1) located near the center of the reverse flow zone. Fig.6B plots the values of the maximum WSS in the reverse flow zone of SB vessel for various BAs. It shows that WSS increases as BA increases for $BA > 10^\circ$ and more importantly, the correlation can be approximated well by a straight line. The correlations are given as follows:

$$\text{Maximum flow rate: } \frac{WSS_{\max}}{\rho U_0^2} [\times 10^2] = 1.42 \left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{12} \right) + 0.34$$

$$\text{Time averaged: } \frac{WSS_{\max}}{\rho U_0^2} [\times 10^2] = 0.97 \left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{12} \right) + 0.11$$

Nondimensionalized WSS distributions along the outer/inner walls of side-branch and distal main-branch are displayed in Fig.7. Previous reports that the WSS on the outer wall of SB is smaller than that on the corresponding inner wall, and that the WSS of the SB decreases as the BA increases (8,11,17). Our study confirmed the tendency reported in the existing literature that the WSS on the outer wall is smaller than that on the corresponding inner wall. This trend was observed not only in the SB but also in the MV. Therefore, it can be said that the WSS in the reverse flow zone of the SB increases with the increase of BA, whereas beyond the reverse flow zone, the WSS in most regions of the SB tends to decrease as BA increases.

DISCUSSION

We conducted a numerical study to investigate the effect of BA on the hemodynamics of branched vessels in cardiovascular flow. We simulated the unsteady equations of the flow field for ten BAs to comprehensively investigate the effect of BA on the flow distribution, pressure drop and reverse flow zone distribution in the coronary bifurcation region. What we found are as follows. 1. Numerical analysis showed that as the BA increased, the pressure drops between the inlet and outlet increased while the flow rate of the SB decreased. 2. The WSS of the outer wall of the SB was lower than that of the corresponding inner wall, and the WSS at the outer wall of the MV distal part was lower than that of the other area. 3. We observed the reverse flow zone along the outer wall side of SB and the maximum WSS in the reverse flow zone increased with the increase of BA. 4. The length of the reverse flow zone in the SB increased rapidly with the increase in the BA to about 20 degrees and then -linearly decreased as BA increased more than 20 degree whereas the height rapidly increased with the increase of BA and approached the asymptotic value of 0.53 as BA increased more beyond around 50°~60°.

Atherosclerotic lesions tend to form in specific areas of the coronary arteries, particularly in regions with low WSS and disrupted blood flow (18). Areas with low WSS are thought to promote endothelial cell dysfunction, leading to increased lipoprotein uptake, upregulation of leukocyte adhesion molecules, and endothelial transmigration of leukocytes, all of which contribute to the development and progression of atherosclerosis (19,20). Because dramatic hemodynamic changes occur at arterial branch points, coronary bifurcations represent a typical environment that influences the progression of atherosclerosis (21,22). Autopsy and intravascular ultrasound studies report that atherosclerosis in coronary bifurcations most commonly occurs on the outer walls of the MV and SB, while it is less frequent in the carina (flow divider) region (23,24). According to a clinical study by van der Giessen et al.

conducted on old-aged individuals with angina, atherosclerosis first develops along the outer wall of a bifurcation (25). As the plaque grows, it expands circumferentially from the outer wall toward the carina. Additionally, in the post-stenotic region along the outer wall, blood flow becomes slower and more turbulent, leading to oscillatory endothelial shear stress (ESS) due to the pulsatile flow (26). This oscillatory ESS further exacerbates the localized atherosclerotic environment, promoting the progression of the lesion. In our study, we also found that WSS is lowest on the outer wall of the SB, and the WSS at the outer wall of the MV distal part was lower than that of the other area, making it a vulnerable area for plaque formation. The unique strength of our findings is that even without plaque formation, the SB in the bifurcation shows a reverse flow zone, and its size and WSS intensity change consistently with the BA. This is clearly demonstrated by the two animations (Mov.1 and Mov.2) that show path lines generated by continuously seeding particles at inlet of the computational domain for the case of two BAs of 30 and 90 degrees. This analysis demonstrated that low flow rate areas and stagnation zones form on the outer wall of the SB (mainly near the ostium). This reverse flow zone may lead to flow stagnation, creating conditions that are conducive to atherosclerosis through mechanisms such as platelet aggregation and lipid deposition.

Coronary bifurcation lesions account for up to 20% of all percutaneous coronary interventions (PCI). Bifurcation lesions are among the most challenging clinical types due to the complexity of the intervention process, frequent ISR, and late stent thrombosis. Zhang et al. studied 1,200 patients with 1,171 bifurcation lesions and examined the impact of BA on SB occlusion after MV stenting during coronary bifurcation intervention (13). This study found that the higher the BA, the higher the SB occlusion rate. Another previous study used pulsatile flow simulations on symmetrical and asymmetrical bifurcation vessels to investigate

the impact of arterial branch angles on the flow field of branch vessels (27). Although this study used a different vessel geometry from our present research, it showed that as the BA increased, the flow rate into the SB vessel decreased. Our experimental results also showed a similar trend, with increasing branch angles resulting in higher pressure drops between the inlet and outlet, along with a reduction in flow rate within the bifurcated vessel. The increased pressure drops and reduced flow rate on the SB side due to larger BA create a favorable environment for atherosclerotic plaque formation, especially in some regions of the vessel, such as the ostium and the outer wall opposite the carina.

The importance of the BA in initiating atherosclerosis in native coronary bifurcation vessels is undisputed. However, there is still debate over how significant BA is in predicting the prognosis of bifurcation vessels with coronary stents in clinical settings. Girasis et al. investigated the impact of BA on 5-year clinical outcomes in patients who underwent PCI for left main coronary artery (LM) as part of the SYNTAX trial. Among the 266 participants, when the distal branch angle before dilation was divided into three groups ($<82^\circ$, 82° - 106° , $\geq 107^\circ$), the rate of major adverse cardiac and cerebrovascular events (MACCE) were numerically higher in larger BA group, however, there were no statistically significant differences ($p = 0.99$) (15). Ki et al. used clinical data from the COBIS registry on coronary bifurcation treatments. They divided 462 patients undergoing LM bifurcation PCI into low LM to left anterior descending coronary artery (LAD) angle and high LM-LAD angle groups using a median branch angle of 152° , then compared target lesion failure over a median 2.87-year follow-up period (28). In patients treated with the crush 2 stent technique, a significantly higher target lesion failure rate, mostly driven by revascularization, was observed in the high LM-LAD angle group compared with the low LM-LAD angle group (35.7% vs. 14.6%; adjusted hazard ratio 3.476; 95% confidence interval 1.612–7.492). On the other hand, another clinical data from the COBIS registry which

divided 1,432 patients into low-angle and high-angle groups using a median branch angle of 50° , the two groups had no significant difference in the rates of MACE or revascularization of target lesions during 21-month follow-up (6.6% vs. 6.9%, $p = 0.856$, and 4.6% vs. 5.7%, $p = 0.375$, respectively) (29). This study was retrospective, and the cutoff may not have been appropriate, with the added limitation of only analyzing non-LM bifurcations. In clinical data of bifurcation PCI, factors other than BA could play more significant role, which can dilute the independent impact of BA. In addition, setting a specific cutoff angle to assess risk is challenging.

Future perspectives and clinical implication

A deeper understanding of the interaction between local flow conditions and the formation and progression of plaques at bifurcation points can improve the ability to prospectively identify areas most likely to develop plaques in high-risk patients. This would allow for hemodynamics-based treatment strategies to improve clinical outcomes. For example, fractional flow reserve (FFR)-based decision-making for moderate stenosis in SB vessels is a guideline-recommended treatment approach, and there have been recent attempts to use non-invasive FFR (angiography-based or CT-based) to guide treatment strategy. The information we obtained on pressure distribution in bifurcations can be used to calibrate this software for more accurate, non-invasive FFR values.

Additionally, if plaque progression is observed in the reverse flow zone of an SB, even if it does not meet the criteria for direct invasive revascularization, we might shorten the intervals for follow-up imaging or functional testing and apply more aggressive lipid-lowering therapy. From a treatment strategy perspective, bifurcation lesions are challenging to stent precisely at the orifice, and even if the stent is properly placed, stent thrombosis and ISR can occur due to

the influence of the reverse flow zone identified in our study. Therefore, drug-coated balloon (DCB) therapy, which leaves no struts behind, could be selectively applied for greater benefit to the patient. As DCB technology has evolved, even in two-stent strategies with a high metal burden, the SB DCB treatment is now being considered as a treatment option. These strategies require further research through randomized controlled trials to verify clinical outcome improvement or non-inferiority compared to conventional stent-based approaches. However, given the local hemodynamics aspect demonstrated in our study, it is theoretically reasonable to apply a strut-free strategy in the SB reverse flow zone, which has low ESS and high oscillatory shear stress.

Limitation

In this experiment, we used a 3D vascular model where the MV extends straight, and the SB originates from the side. This typically corresponds to non-LM bifurcations in actual coronary arteries. In patients' coronary arteries, LM bifurcations often don't have a straight structure between the LM and the left anterior descending artery, so our results cannot be directly applied or interpreted for those vessel configurations. Additionally, although we applied unsteady pulsatile waveforms in this experiment, the 3D vessel shape used a rigid pipe model, so it did not incorporate the elasticity or cyclic strain characteristics of actual coronary arteries. Further studies using fluid-structure interaction could address these limitations.

CONCLUSIONS

A three-dimensional flow of a side branch vessel (SB) bifurcating with a given angle from a main straight vessel was numerically examined. Unsteady pulsatile flow was considered at $Re=312$, which is based on the inlet mean velocity, diameter of the coronary vessel and the kinematic viscosity of blood, which was assumed to be a Newtonian fluid. The bifurcating flow had a bigger pressure drop with a smaller flow rate to the side branch vessel as the

bifurcation angle (BA) increased. The reverse flow of SB began to appear with the BA bigger than 10 degrees because blood has a lower momentum as BA increases near the outer wall that is subject to adverse pressure gradient. The height/strength of reverse flow zone was found to increase with the increase of BA implying that the larger BA is, the narrower the flow passage of SB is leading to the occlusion of SB. The presence of a reverse flow zone indicates that blood flow is likely to become stagnant. Flow stagnation can lead to early atherosclerosis in native vessels, while in stented vessels, it can cause stent thrombosis or ISR.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no financial conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

Conceptualization, K.Y.L. and H.G.C.; data curation and formal analysis, S.T.H.; funding acquisition, K.Y.L. and J.Y.Y.; investigation, D.H.V.; methodology, S.T.H., H.G.C. and D.H.V.; project administration, K.Y.L.; resources, J.Y.Y.; supervision, K.Y.L.; validation and visualization, D.H.V.; writing—original draft, K.Y.L., S.T.H. and H.G.C.; writing—review & editing, K.Y.L., and H.G.C..

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability Statement

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and its supplementary materials.

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FIGURE AND FIGURE LEGENDS

Fig.1 Computational domain and boundary conditions

(A) Computational domain with unstructured mesh (B) Pulsatile velocity at Inlet

(C) Schematic of computational domain

Fig.2 Flowrate to SB and pressure drop for various BAs

(A) Ratio of SB flowrate to inlet flowrate for various BAs

(B) Pressure drops for various BAs

Fig.3 Contours and profiles of V_s on the cross-section of SB inlet

(A) Contours of V_s on the cross-section of SB inlet

(B) Profiles of V_s along the lines of A-B and C-D (Time-averaged)

Fig.4 Profiles of static pressures along the outer/inner walls of SB for various BAs

Fig.5 Y-velocity contours of reverse flow zone and its height/length for various BAs

(A) Contours of y-component velocity for the three BAs on the symmetric plane

(B) Lengths of the reverse flow zone

(C) Heights of the reverse flow zone

Fig.6 WSS contours of reverse flow zone and plot of the maximum WSS for various BAs

(A) WSS contours on the outer wall of SB

(B) Plots of the maximum WSS

Fig.7 WSS profiles along the walls of SB and MV for various BAs

Mov.1 Numerical simulations of the bifurcating flow model with a 30-degree bifurcation angle. The reverse flow zone is observed along the outer wall side of the side branch. The length of the reverse flow zone is longer, and the height of the reverse flow zone is lower (narrower) than 90-degree model.

30degree_zoomin_final_6.avi

Mov.2 Numerical simulations of the bifurcating flow model with a 90-degree bifurcation angle. The reverse flow zone is observed along the outer wall side of the side branch. The length of the reverse flow zone is shorter, and the height of the reverse flow zone is higher (wider) than 30-degree model.

90degree_zoomin_final_6.avi

SUPPLEMENTARY

Fig.S1 Results of grid/time-step independent test

(A) Grid independence test

(B) Time-step dependence test

(C) Grid/time-step independent solution

Fig.S2 Profiles of V_s along the lines of A-B and C-D (at the instant of Max-inlet velocity)

Fig.7 WSS profiles along the walls of SB and MV for various BAs

